

Deliverable D1.2

Report on selected indicators, together with their related data sources

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1. Introduction

The FoodSafeR project aims to develop an innovative and holistic proactive food safety warning and management system, with identification of emerging risks a central focus. In order to create this system, it is necessary to first identify anticipated changes in the European food safety arena.

This deliverable report D1.2 relates to the work performed under Task 1.2 (Identification of indicators and data for food safety risk emergence), which aims to identify the indicators and corresponding data sources for food safety risk emergence, related to the trends, drivers and sub-drivers of changes in the food production system and its environment that might be related to food safety. The drivers and sub-drivers have been previously identified in Task 1.1 (Analysis of drivers and key influencing factors for food safety risk emergence).

The results of Task 1.2 will serve as input to the requirements definition and development in WP4 of the open digital hub. Our approach is to create a list of "INDICATORS" which will be used as keywords to search within a list of "DATABASES or WEBSITES". In this report, some databases related to specific indicators have been determined already. In the next phase of the project, we will have a dedicated section on the platform (being developed in WP4) that will display graphics and information about all the "fixed terms" or "INDICATORS" from WP1. If these terms appear in any database or website from WP1 (and depending on their accessibility credentials, which will need to be studied for each specific case), they will be shown on the platform, as part of WP4.

Below, a summary of Task 1.2 is given. The first three points refer to the content of this Deliverable report D1.2, whereas points 4 to 7 refer IT functionality which will be developed in WP4 for the open digital hub.

WP1 – Task 1.2:

- For each of the prioritized stressors for the emergence of food safety hazards and related risks identified in Task 1.1, one or more indicators will be identified and/or established.
- Available data and datasets on these indicators will be searched for from open-source databases.
- T1.2 will be supplied with the necessary input from T1.1 on drivers and barriers.

WP4

- This data will be linked to the open digital hub (WP4), such that the platform dashboard displays the real-time values of the indicators, based on underlying data.
- Risk managers can follow the trends in the indicators, reflecting potential relevant changes in our food system and its environment that may lead to the emergence of food safety hazards and related risks.
- Alerts will be given in case indicators tend to move out of the 'normal' range of values.
- The process of crawling available databases and aggregating the resulting information, will make it possible for analytics to reveal hidden/underlying trends and patterns, mainly to identify changes in the stressors and information on their impact on toxicity of the hazards. This will support the prioritization of the indicators and emerging hazards, as well as to identify data gaps.

Hence, within the scope of WP1 and the current deliverable, the focus will be on identifying indicators and associated data sources.

2. Materials and Methods

The drivers and sub-drivers developed in Task 1.1 (Analysis of drivers and key influencing factors for food safety risk emergence) have been used as starting point for identification of indicators. For one (sub)driver, one or more indicators can be identified. Indicators were first identified – per (sub) driver using literature and open available sources. From these, a gross list of indicators was established.

Next, a Living Lab 3 workshop was held with project partners to verify the identified indicators, and add missing indicators, if any. Also databases related to each indicators were identified, where possible.

2.1 Workshop “Indicators for drivers of emerging food safety hazards”

FoodSafeR Living Lab 3 was designed to **identify indicators for drivers of emerging food safety hazards**, which built on the workshop in 2023 where trends, drivers and barriers of food safety risks were identified. These drivers for hazards and risks which were already assembled and analysed in the FoodSafeR project were introduced in the first part of the Living Lab. In this Living Lab 3 we **focused on indicators**, measurable factors that point to or are related to the occurrence of hazards or risks.

2.1.1 Short definition of drivers and indicators

Drivers

- are developments fostering change which affect or shape the future.
- are shaping how a society, organisation, industry, research area, technology, etc. develops (EFSA, 2010)
- can directly influence the food system and also extend beyond the food system into other aspects of society

Indicators

- A **measurable factor** (with a unit e.g. temperature in Celsius)
- indicates or is directly or indirectly **related to the possibility of the occurrence** of a (re)-emerging hazard or risk or in this project a driver (e.g. ‘storage and transport conditions’),
- provides **information on the nature** of the hazard or driver and source of risk,
- ideally it is **reliable, sensitive and quantifiable**, but can either be **qualitative** or **quantitative** in nature

2.1.2 Introduction to the task

Aim: finding indicator(s) to monitor subdrivers of emerging food safety hazards.

The guiding questions during the Living Lab were as follows:

- (1) Which **measurable “indicators”** can be used to monitor the subdriver?

- (2) Is the indicator linked to any **database** you are familiar with? If yes, which databases are they? If no, is there anything related to the indicator? Are they accessible/open source?
- (3) In case several indicators were mentioned: Which **indicator** do you consider as the **most relevant one for the subdriver**?

2.1.3 Methodology

LL3 was organized online to support a participatory approach in the analysis of indicators for drivers and key influencing factors for food safety risk emergence. The FoodSafeR consortium and scientific advisory board were invited to join the Living Lab via Zoom. 70 people participated in the Living Lab and discussed in 5 breakout rooms potential indicators of 2 (and in one group 3) drivers on a Mural Whiteboard. A list of participants can be found in the Appendix. The distribution of drivers across the 5 groups is the following:

1. Distribution / Environmental contamination
2. Management of (natural) resources / Demographic development
3. Technologies in food production / Health & Wellbeing
4. Legislation, policies & governance / Technologies in food processing
5. Consumer behaviour / Bioprocesses / Geopolitical instability

The drivers were shortly presented to all participants in the beginning of the Living Lab. When the participants were sent into the breakout rooms, a moderator presented the 2-3 drivers relevant for the group discussion in more detail. The moderators facilitated the two discussion sessions among the 7-8 participants in each of the breakout rooms.

3. Results

3.1 Workshop

The results of the workshop are sorted according to the STEEP factors as given in Figure 3.1. Each section starts with a description of the driver and according subdrivers (*in grey – because their definition was not the focus of the Living Lab*), followed by a screenshot of participant's input on the Mural Whiteboard and ends with a list of indicators (in black) for each subdriver (indicators concerning a similar topic were grouped together).

NOTE: References to data or databases are marked in **BLUE**, text marked in **BOLD** shows if the indicators or databases were marked as **most relevant** by participants

Figure 3.1: Overview of drivers and sub-drivers

3.1.1 Social Drivers

(a) Consumer behaviour

The behaviour of individual consumers can influence nutritional habits/individual diets. (Changed eating habits can lead to potential exposure or development of new hazards).

- **Dietary choice:** What food consumers choose based on nutrition and preference; e.g., vegetarian, fast food, red meat
- **Consumer knowledge:** The individual and common knowledge of consumers in relation to food (including education & training); e.g., cooking at home, hygiene practices
- **Consumer awareness/attitude:** Change of attitude drives choices; e.g., animal welfare, natural equals safe, herbal tea is good for you

- **Public awareness:** The awareness on foods, diets and related hazards via governmental communication, news, social media, NGOs; e.g., high fibre, low salt, bird flu, antimicrobial resistance

Figure 3.2: Overview of indicators for consumer behaviour

Dietary Choice indicators

- Red meat consumption per capita per year
- **Consumption of diff. types of food / Consumption per Capita/ Consumption of various types of food**
- **Dietary lifestyle: omnivore, vegetarian, flexitarian, novel protein sources (e.g. insects) etc.**
- **Number of new vegetarian or vegan restaurants (trend).**
- **Volume and amounts of production / Demand is also related with Risks**
- **National Sensus data / Availability may be an issue**
- Implication of seasonal in dietary choices & Consumption
- **Index - Appearance (emerging) Novel types of food**
- **Amount of people with certain illnesses => Epidemiological Data**
- Increase risk to heavy metals with increased plant based food e.g. monitor Arsenic in brown rice
- Use of food supplements such as vitamins and minerals (risk to overdose)
- Accumulation of (plant-based) toxins as alkaloids

Consumer knowledge indicators everything measurable through surveys - information channels they consult (official, private, Social Media...)

- Knowledge of safe food preparation (e.g. judging "doneness" of chicken)
- Hand hygiene practices during meal preparation
- **Cleaning of food preparation surfaces and kitchenware**
- **Survey & Interviews on cooking and hygienic practices**
- **QR-Codes to know how often people search for something**
- **Measuring their interest on getting information / How many times do they look for xx in Social Media or Internet in general**
- **Consumer trends linked to knowledge? - how?**
- Knowledge of safe and sustainable food packaging
- **Survey on Health Benefits**
- **Screening Social Media / ranking what type and how often visited are hygienic and cooking practices related videos**
- Comparing organic waste types / (see also Consumer awareness below)

Consumer awareness / attitude indicators

- Knowledge is also a driver of awareness
- **Quantity of food lost as an index of food preservation**
- **Measuring waste as a way to know knowledge on food preservation**
- Attitudes towards animal welfare
- **amount of people going to local farmer's shops**
- Willingness to replace meat with alternative protein sources e.g. insects, lab cultured meat
- Attitudes on most important characteristics of sustainable food
- Extent of implementation of safety practices
- Awareness of various food safety topics

Public awareness indicators

- presence of microplastics in food
- Country using labelling on food --> society is informed about it
- **Indicator of public awareness: use of octagonal labelling, use of traffic light labels in food products**
- **Measuring the sales of certain labelled product**
- **SafeConsume HE Project -- Survey and data collection <https://safeconsume.eu/>**
- **Eurobarometer on Food Safety in EU - data on consumer behavior/awareness <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/it/corporate/pub/eurobarometer22> (see section 3.2, page 43 for further details and specific links)**
- **Consumer selection/ranking of various dietary behaviours to improve health**

(b) Demographic development

Demographic development strongly influences dietary and nutritional needs in Europe through:

- **Population change:** Change in the size of a population between a given time period (usually one year); e.g., birth/deaths, age/population pyramid

- **Prevalence of vulnerable groups:** Composition of the population considering e.g., ageing, immunocompromised people
- **Urbanisation:** Proportion of people living in towns and cities
- **Social welfare:** The welfare of society, esp. of those segments of society that are underprivileged or disadvantaged because of poverty, poor education, unemployment, etc.
- **Migration:** Migration movement, and on a small scale also tourism and travelling of people lead to cultural changes; e.g., exposure to different foods/hazards

Figure 3.3: Overview of indicators for demographic development

Population change indicators

- Immigration - European Commission, Eurostat
- **Demographics of population**
- Ageing of the general population
- **Population size (Eurostat)**
- less young people available for agricultural work
- Birth rate
- e.g. <https://data.oecd.org/pop/population.htm>¹
- <https://population.un.org/wpp/>¹

¹ Added from desktop research

Prevalence of vulnerable groups indicators

- Income per household
- Diabetes statistics
- Prevalence of immunosuppression (US?)
- **cancer statistics**
- Prevalence of allergies, intolerances, chronic diseases of the gut (i.e. Celiac, Crohn's)
- Homeless populations, impacting food security
- Population numbers in different age classes (ageing?)
- **In general: diseases related to metabolism and coronary diseases**
- mobility problems

Urbanisation indicators

- **Degree of urbanization (eurostat)**
- Monitoring the change of the population ratio between urban and rural areas
- Land conversion from forest to agriculture
- **Education rate (influencing food consumption habits)**
- Access to high quality food (food deserts) in both cities and rural areas (access to supermarkets or convenience markets)
- Gap between agriculture and consumer: food safety knowledge, food competency, ...?
- Access to green spaces/Education as to where food comes from

Social welfare indicators

- **Gap between rich and poor is increasing, purchase behavior**
- Number of people supported by unemployment, workers compensation, etc.
- Degree of sanitation - people living in households with basic sanitary facilities
- Amount of subvention of healthy, national food/agriculture for food to be affordable

Migration indicators

- **Legislation and number regarding migration in every country**
- Proportion of population travelling to exotic destinations
- Illegal import of food products from other locations (global food trade)
- Monitoring the number of immigrants involved in agriculture and food production

(c) Health and wellbeing (of human beings)

Human health and wellbeing can affect the susceptibility of the general public to food safety risks.

- **Human health condition:** A person's wellbeing influenced by proportion of non-communicable diseases; e.g., depression, diabetes or obesity
- **Perceived human health condition:** E.g., allergies, intolerances, herbal teas, supplements
- **Resistant pests and diseases:** Pests and diseases can develop different resistances; e.g., antibiotic use and related antimicrobial resistance

Figure 3.4: Overview of indicators for health and wellbeing

Human health condition indicators

- National level of obesity etc. from Dept of Health
- National surveys linking disease to food intake
- <https://www.sciensano.be/en/projects/national-food-consumption-survey#physical-activity-and-sedentary-behaviour>
- Occurrence of NCDs
- Overall life expectancy
- Colon cancer rates (FAO, EFSA)
- <https://www.sciensano.be/en/health-information>
- Allergies (could be increased due to insect consumption)
- Rates of intolerances (e.g. milk) in population (*a rapid raise could be an indication for a food born cause*)
- Rates of antibiotic residues in waste water

Perceived human health condition indicators

- Rates of allergies or intolerances reported by consumers e.g. surveys
- Antibiotic resistance reported (due to excessive application on the field / farmers & consumers affected) --> applicable for new, high-productive varieties which are quite sensitive; reason why old varieties are more resistant
- Rate of undetected allergies and intolerances (due to "old" protein parameters in ambulances to detect allergies)

Resistant pests and diseases indicators

- Rates of antimicrobial resistance
- Rate of multi-resistant strains
- **Rates of antibiotic dispensing/use** / Overuse of antibiotics in human medicine and animal production
- **Record of agricultural management practices** (crop rotation and others can prevent high disease pressures) / Information on farmers to receive subsidies (**database for management practices**, e.g. Agricultural chamber in Austria?)

3.1.2 Technological Drivers

(a) Technologies in food production

Technological cross-overs may lead to new products and production systems. While some technologies can decrease the risk of hazards, others may cause unwanted side effects.

- **Primary production:** Technologies used for the production, rearing or growing of primary products; e.g., industrialized, traditional, intensive - extensive (incl. fishing, hunting and harvesting of wild products)
 - Plant-derived food production
 - Animal-derived food production
- **Products for food production:** Products used in food production to increase the health of livestock or for protecting and enhancing crops; e.g., food yield increasing measures (pesticide, fertilizers and its alternatives), insects for feed, measures to clean the stables
- **Bioengineering:** Bioengineered foods have been modified through genetic techniques; e.g., enzymatic engineering and GMO's: GMO maize, golden rice, lab grown meat
- **Novel food sources:** Production of e.g., insects, algae for human consumption

Figure 3.5: Overview of indicators for technologies in food production

Primary production indicators

- Level fertilizer/perstice detective in waste water (water quality databases?)
- Purchase rates/numbers for innovative machines
- Amount of urban gardening
- Price fluctuations
- Global fish production (high intensity farming --> high antibiotics use)
- Indoor – outdoor production rates
- Rates of animal/plant based products
- Rates of organic farming

Plant-derived food production

- Statistics about vegetarian/vegan population
- https://smartproteinproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/Smart-Protein-European-Consumer-Survey_2023.pdf
- Use of "new", high-productive (sensitive) varieties by farmers (which require more pesticides --> higher risks for consumer)

Animal-derived food production

- Number of intensive livestock holdings
- Size of farms
- Rates of fishing

Products for food production indicators

- Use of fertilizer, pesticides, veterinary drug
- Purchase rates/numbers for innovative fertilizers
- **Purchase rates/numbers for innovative pesticides**
- Approved new licenses for fertilizer/pesticides
- <https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/active-substances>
- Number of insect farmers
- Number of insect rearers in Europe
- Amount of indoor produced food

Bioengineering indicators

- Share of GMO cultivation
- Use of genetic modified plants (>emerging mycotoxins?)
- GMO applications to Commission/ **EFSA**
- **Production rates of GMO foods**
- **Database GMO monitoring: ISAAA**
- Transfer of genetic traits

Novel food sources indicators

- **Consumer consumption rates of novel foods e.g. insects, plant-based meat alternatives**
- Consumer interest/ Market trends
- Insect/algae production for food
- Rates of cell-based food products
- **Novel food applications to the Commission/ EFSA**
Summary of applications and notifications https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/novel-food/authorisations/summary-applications-and-notifications_en
- **Fermented foods from industry and home (social media posts)**
- Overdose of certain vitamins or minerals (due to intake of supplements or herbal teas)
- **Production rates of supplements etc. https://foodsupplementseurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/FSE-Consumer_Survey-Ipsos-2022.pdf**

(b) Technologies in food processing

Innovative technologies lead to improved, more sustainable food products with longer shelf lives within whole supply chain. Some technologies may bear the risk of unwanted side products, or on the other hand may decrease the risk of hazards.

- **Processing techniques and scale:** 'Processing' means any action that substantially alters the initial product; e.g., heating, smoking, curing, maturing, drying, marinating, extraction, extrusion, novel and alternative techniques and industrial and traditional processes or a combination of those processes, risk of cross-contamination
- **Food packaging:** Containment of food; e.g., primary/secondary contained, food packaging material, type and duration of contact, smart packaging
- **Upcycling for food:** Using of side streams in the food chain; e.g., coffee grounds to grow mushrooms

➤ **New technologies: Monitoring processes and products; e.g., AI, big data, blockchain analysis**

Figure 3.6: Overview of indicators for technologies in food processing

Notes and discussion points:

Inflation above everything, general impact

- Sources?
- Legal and ethical limitation on web scraping
- Sharing data to be used beyond scientific purposes?
- Data sharing may ruin the business models
- Useful data often comes from reports that are not necessarily databases
- Suggestion for new technologies: narrow down
- Mainstreaming / wide scale adoption

Processing techniques and scale indicators

- Digital media monitoring EUM EMM Overview (newsbrief.eu) / TIM tool (TIM analytics | TIM analytics | Knowledge for policy (europa.eu))
- Monitoring trade publications for announcements
- Euromonitor/Kantar data to monitor new foods on the market
- Percentage of food that was heat treated (?)
- Increase of minimally processed foods
- Percentage of food processed using a specific technique

- Percentage of preserved food
- Food waste: shelf life extension / redistribution
- Euromonitor
- Web scraping retail stores and ingredient lists
- Watching developments in more advanced countries i.e. lab based meat in Singapore
- Food formulation e.g. minimally processed raw material
- Price fluctuations
- Amount of convenience food
- Economic size of food business operator

Food packaging indicators

- Proper labelling of packaging
- Plastic Europe association: Plastics Europe • Enabling a sustainable future
- Percentage of recycled material
- Residues in recycled material
- Patents of food contact materials
- Industry information about the packaging material that is used
- Amount of plastic material from packaging
- Percentage of properly labelled packaging
- Changes in technology used for packaging (safety)
- Smart biosensor packaging materials - spoilage indicators
- TIM tool (TIM analytics | TIM analytics | Knowledge for policy (europa.eu))
- RASFF: migration alerts Food contact materials
number of RASFF alerts concerning packaging
- Accumulation of harmful substances

Upcycling for food indicators

- Amount of by-products discarded (where is it going?)
- The type of processing used in upcycling (raw, heating?)
- Change in cost-efficiency of upcycling
- Food waste cascading (annual reporting)
- Food waste at EU DG Sante: food waste platform Food waste reduction targets - European Commission (europa.eu)
- Food waste rates

New technologies indicators

- **Lab-based meat**
 - Precision Fermentation
 - 3D printed foods
 - Risk from ingredients, allergens
 - Plasma low temp resulting in an increase in biogenic amines
 - Novel food catalogue <https://ec.europa.eu/food/food-feed-portal/screen/novel-food-catalogue/search>
- Automation
- Online real time-monitoring
- IoT / Cloud
- (General) rise in cyber attacks on platforms used by food companies

- E.g. attack on JBS systems
- Digitalization level of food business operator
- Overreliance on digitalisation
- Failure of digital tools in terms of monitoring
- Emergence of new technologies

3.1.3 Economic Drivers

(a) Distribution

Across the food sector, a significant horizontal and vertical restructuring is happening which effects distribution along the food supply chain.

- **Global trade:** The exchange of capital, goods, and services across international borders or territories, including trade agreements; e.g., jute bag for food contact material, imported fish
- **Distribution channels:** Well-established paths to move products from the manufacturer to the consumer; e.g., supermarkets, local farmers' market, wholesale
- **New distribution channels:** New paths to move products from the manufacturer to the consumer; e.g., digital marketplaces, ghost kitchens, pop-up stores
- **Food fraud:** Any deliberate action of businesses or individuals to deceive others in regards to the integrity of food to gain undue advantage; e.g., melamine in milk, incorrect veterinary drug use, racemic mixtures
- **Storage:** process of keeping cooked food and raw materials in favorable conditions that will prolong their shelf-life while preventing the growth of harmful microorganisms

Figure 3.7: Overview of indicators for distribution

Global trade indicators

- International trade in good statistics - Distinguish global trade for food
 - Import in euros per year
 - Export in euros per year
 - **FAO? specify sectors**
 - Economic metrics e.g. GDP
- Inflation
- Recession
- Economic globalisation indicators
- Number of conflicts and wars
- **WTO, Sanitary & Phytosanitary measures**
- Closed borders
- **Discuss with economists for databases**
- Geopolitical developments influence global trade
- **<https://databank.worldbank.org/>**
- Price fluctuations
- **ECDC EFSA outbreak reports**
- **Economic Intelligence unit platform for trade/commodity/economy data**

Distribution channels indicators

- Market share of delivery companies
- Supermarket market share
- Containers blocked in ports
- Fluidity of shipping modes e.g. blocked Suez channel
- Number of trucks used for transport
- **Sales data**
- Northern Ireland as example of market perturbations (EU-UK)
- <https://www.nisra.gov.uk/statistics/business-statistics/broad-economy-sales-and-exports-statistics>
- Number of weekly markets
- Number of local food markets
- No. of Food Banks (support systems)
- Data sharing / users on data sharing platforms / articles published
- Cost of Amount of users of data sharing platforms
- **Consumer studies** where they buy products

New distribution channels indicators

- Market share of ghost kitchens
- Numbers of studies published on new distribution channels
- New start-ups
- **Online shops**
- e-commerce
- **Growth of novel delivery modes**
- Trade Deals (UK esp.)

Food fraud indicators

- Peer reviewed papers
- Articles in news papers
- **JRC Tech report (EC)**
- Recalls
- **RASFF alerts**
- Amount of alerts in EFSA network
- <https://www.safefood.net/> safefood is an all-island body, set up under the British-Irish Agreement Act 1999.
- Weather impact on commodities
- Harvest forecast
- Price forecast
- Number of insolvency in the food sector
- **Food Fraud Database** <https://www.foodchainid.com/products/food-fraud-database/>
- Link to EU Agri Food Fraud Network page with enforcement actions, reports and publications: https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/eu-agri-food-fraud-network_en

Storage indicators

- Time (how long)
- Food waste measurements
- Energy and electricity consumption
- **Energy costs**

- Price of fuel
- Cost of storage
- Temperature & Outdoor temperature
- **How much storage space is there?** Square meter storage space Food business operator
- Consumer research metrics on cooking habits

3.1.4 Environmental Drivers

(a) Environmental contamination

Environmental contamination influences competition for land and shortage of available water due to over-exploitation, pollution, the impact of climate change.

- **Agricultural pollution:** Pollution of air, land and water caused by agriculture; e.g., leaching of chemicals, veterinary product residues, plastic waste and eutrophication
- **Pollution:** Pollution from the original extraction and use of non-food raw material in the primary production or manufacturing of goods; e.g., metal mining, fossil fuel use
- **Sewage treatment:** Sewage treatment plant, both industrial and municipal; e.g., incomplete treatment or effluents released into the environment
- **Waste management:** Personal, local, regional, industrial management of waste (collection, separation, processing and storage) which can be organized or unorganized (open dumping or burning) and can cause leachates into the environment

Figure 3.8: Overview of indicators for environmental contamination

Agricultural pollution indicators

- Chemical **Fertilizer** Usage - (Hazards Cd, As, U)
- Ammonia Emission by agriculture
- Overuse of fertilizers leading to harmful algal blooms
- Use of manure for fertilizing
- Nitrate concentration in water (check for reports)
- **Pesticides sold per year**
- **Fertilizers sold per year**
- Microplastic concentration in soil and water
- Occurrence of dioxin and mycotoxins in feed
- **Usage of antibiotics --> e.g. sales data**
- AMR (genes; MIC)
- **Reports Antibiotic sales and AMR doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7209 (AMR); + ESVAC report (sales data)**
- Level of soil/water pollution
- Greenhouse gas emission by agriculture
- Surface runoff and water holding capacity
- Livestock lameness [Hazard - dermal footbaths – indicator for Cu & Zn pollution]
- **Newspaper articles + social media**
- Rates of water infiltration
- Root density
- Increase of phytotoxins in seafood

Pollution indicators

- Air quality measurements
Air quality database 2022 <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/air-pollution/who-air-quality-database/2022>
- Amount of rain - deviation from mean rain fall
- **Your gateway to the EU, News, Highlights | European Union <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/EDGAR>**
- Soil pollution measurements at building sites
- Fossil fuel extraction or use
- Fracking used in country /neighbourhood
- Metal mining in Europe
- **Fossil fuel share in gross available energy**
- **LUCAS soil database (Geogenic baselines) <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/lucas>**
- **EU Soils Mission EJP Soil Benchmarks NI Soil Nutrient & Health Scheme** - link up to other projects under Soil mission?
- **Microbial contamination [e.g. growth of fecal bacteria, check national databases?**

Sewage treatment indicators

- **HydroWASTE <https://www.hydrosheds.org/products/hydrowaste>**

- Home | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations <https://www.fao.org/aquastat/en/overview/methodology/wastewater>
- Global wastewater database <https://www.iwmi.cgiar.org/2014/06/global-wastewater-database/>
- AMR genes
- Microbial load
- Presence of indicator organisms
- Recent publications on these indicators, might be something being available publicly in the future
- Irrigation practises
- **Degree of waste water treatment**
- Costs for sewage treatment
- No. of treatment steps
- Number and size of sewage treatment plants
- Quality and number of sewage plants for water management
- Production of struvite. i.e Dublin Ringsend

Waste management indicators

- Accumulation of harmful substances
- Food loss / Food waste index - e.g FAO on global level
- Amount of waste in a country per capita
- Waste heaps/dumps amount or size
- River and water plastic (plastic soup) – reports on amount?
- Number of criminal charges due to illegal waste disposal
- **Recycling rate**
- Incineration usage/strategy/technology
- Incinerated waste
- Waste collection facilities
- Municipal solid waste MSW compost rates
- Landfill tax levels
- Your gateway to the EU, News, Highlights | European Union <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/waste/database> (refer to section 3.2 for further details and specific links)
- Info from stores on deposit system

(b) Management of (natural) resources

The availability, accessibility and usability of natural resources are prerequisites for prospering economies including the agricultural sectors. High quality land and the availability of water and nutrients are the basis for food and renewable energy production.

- **Recycling:** Any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes; e.g., removing heavy metal, smelting of e-waste
- **Use of waste stream:** Using of other water sources and reusing waste including sludge, manure and fish effluent to recapture the nutrients still present for agriculture

- **Water and soil management:** The planning, developing, distributing and optimum use of water resources and application of operations, practices, and treatments to protect soil; e.g, nutrient sourcing and use

Figure 3.9: Overview of indicators for management of (natural) resources

Recycling indicators

- Number of industries for recycling agricultural waste in the area (**National record of industries**)
- Waste recycling rates
- Recycling rates of e-waste
- **Recycling rate (eurostat)**
- Food waste, packaging waste, municipal waste
- **Rapid Alert recalls / non-compliance with food contact material legislation if recycled materials are used in food packaging**
- Food packaging contribution to chemical exposure
- Accumulation of harmful substances (mycotoxins, PFAS, heavy metals)
- Chemicals measured in environment
- Material prices for recyclates
- Shelf life labelling

Use of waste stream indicators

- **Use of organic fertilizers / manure in agriculture**
- CFU monitoring data from water used downstream
- BOD of water used

- Rates of water infiltration, water quality
- Level of soil/water pollution
- Amount of organic food waste - wasted vs. composted
- Raw material consumption
- Manure storage
- Heavy metals emission

Water and soil management indicators

- **Plastics in soils (microplastics) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-023-00967-2> Analysis of microplastics (umweltbundesamt.at)**
- Monitoring use of antibiotics in farm animals
- **Predictions of crop production in tons in relation to natural toxins (OECD)**
- Heavy metal concentrations in soils
- Reduction of contaminated crops by prediction
- **Proportion of land used for animal farming (FAO)**
- **Predictions/Evolution of pesticides sales (OECD)**
- **Nutrient composition of soil (C, N, P) - BORIS - Bodeninformationssystem (umweltbundesamt.at)**
- Monitoring of drought conditions (rainfall measurements, desertification)
- Occurrence of flooding, extreme weather causing run-off
- **Eutrophication of water bodies (European Marine Observation and Data Network - EMOD)**
- **Microbial quality of water and soil**
- Agricultural area under organic farming
- Irrigation
- Water abstraction
- Surface runoff and water holding capacity
- Aeration, cohesion
- Intensification / extensification
- Water holding capacity
- Root density
- Chemicals measured in environment in ppm

(c) Bioprocesses

The increase in zoonotic diseases running along with an increase in resistance to drugs, such as antibiotics, increase the threat to both humans and nature and thereby influence the food system.

- **Transboundary pests and diseases:** Pests and diseases which spread between farms, countries and continents (due to climate) in a OneHealth society; e.g., swine flu
- **Bio-accumulation:** Bio-accumulation is defined as the net accumulation of a contaminant in or on an organism from all sources including water, air, and diet; e.g., heavy metal in fish

Figure 3.10: Overview of indicators for bioprocesses

Transboundary pests and diseases indicators

- Appearance of Bio-vectors (insects) in new regions <= Climate change
- Continuous Monitoring of pests
- Changes in organisms that change the "ecology" (Context) - Modelling using diff. Data
- Agricultural pests are linked with vectors amounts
- Number of confiscated food (Data bases of airports and marine ports)
- Scale of FOODI trade (export and import)
- Monitoring spikes and shifts could be confined to other shifts
- Pathogen monitoring reports (Animal and Plants)
- Spread of (zoonotic) diseases

Bio-accumulation indicators

- Monitoring of Antimicrobial residues / regularly done
- Rapid Alert system for food and feed
- Presence of Bacteria in Water (Waste water monitoring systems in PLace) e.g., Covid measured in Water
- Relation to animal Feed
- Accumulation of contaminant in animals (bees, worms)
- Biodiversity indicators (loss of biodiversity)
- National Monitoring Programms => Indicators from Environmental Health?
- Accumulation of (plant-based) toxins as alkaloids
- Increase risk to heavy metals with increased plant based food eg. monitor Arsenic in brown rice

3.1.5 Political Drivers

(a) Legislation, policies and governance

Standardization, legislation, policy and governance directly and indirectly influence production and consumption of food.

- **Monitoring and communication of food safety:** Food safety monitoring is the mechanism that routinely checks for safety hazards, manages compliance adherence, and ensures procedures are being correctly implemented and communicated openly; e.g., inspectors, food business operators recalls, RASFF
- **Good practices and standards:** Practices that have been proven to work well and produce good results, and is therefore recommended as a model; e.g., ISO standards, hygiene
- **Food legislation:** Legislation which regulates the production, trade and handling of food across the entire food chain, from the provision for animal feed to the consumer; e.g., HACCP, food contact material
- **Food information:** Information concerning a food and made available to the final consumer by means of a label, and other accompanying material through modern technology tools or verbal communication; e.g., nutritional labelling, ingredient list, private labels of quality, source, etc.

Figure 3.11: Overview of indicators for legislation, policies and governance

Notes and discussion points:

- Open access and public availability vs. internal use
- Using specific keywords related to food safety in broader databases
- Do we have the data? Is it public (recalls)
- Monitoring spikes and shifts could be confined to other shifts
- There may be a lot of factors impacting a specific indicator
- Which indicators are independent, e.g. what causes recalls?
- How reliable are the indicators? (e.g. from a consultancy)
- Data as service

Monitoring and communication of food safety indicators

- Digital media monitoring EUM EMM Overview (newsbrief.eu) / TIM tool (TIM analytics | TIM analytics | Knowledge for policy (europa.eu)) - Social listening
- Belgian food safety authority barometer to communicate with stakeholders on food safety : <https://www.favv-afscab.be/scientificcommittee/barometer/>
- Annual national reports on food safety (e.g. in Austria)
- The European Union One Health 2022 Zoonoses Report; <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/8442>
- Monitoring of veterinary drugs EU https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/chemical-safety/residues-veterinary-medicinal-products_en
- Pesticides data programme annual report from EFSA : <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/7939>
- New Interfaces for inter-agency communication
- food fraud monitoring in EU JRC reports : https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/food-fraud-quality/monthly-food-fraud-summary-reports_en
- EFSA zoonoses report annual <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/8442>
- <https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/Lebensmittel/lebensmittelkontrolle/LMSicherheit.html>
- Pesticide Data Program | Agricultural Marketing Service (usda.gov)
- RASFF (for authorities)
- FDA Total Diet Study (TDS) <https://www.fda.gov/food/reference-databases-and-monitoring-programs-food/fda-total-diet-study-tds>
- Availability of surveillance data
- Official controls and communication
- Emergence of recalls e.g. Belgium FAVV - Productterugroepingen (favv-afscab.be)
- The European Union Summary Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in zoonotic and indicator bacteria from humans, animals and food in 2020/2021: <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7867>
- Zoonotic agents, German database: <https://zoonotify.bfr.berlin/>
- Number of technical measurements for legal standards

Good practices and standards indicators

- Standards : Codex Alimentarius <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/codex-texts/list-standards/en/>

- EU platform on guidance platform : https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/biological-safety/food-hygiene/guidance-platform_en

Food legislation indicators

- Pesticide residues database
- Veterinary databases
- <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/veterinary-regulatory-overview/research-and-development-veterinary-medicines/maximum-residue-limits-mrl#ema-inpage-item-10712>
- **EU regulation ==> EURLEX website**
- EU database pesticide https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database_en
- EU database additives regulation <https://ec.europa.eu/food/food-feed-portal/screen/food-additives/search>
- EU Monitor: Always up to date with the latest developments with the EU Monitor/1/j9tvgaicovz8izf_j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vk0qgtdhw4yx <https://www.eumonitor.nl/9353000>
- Change in legislation (actual, expected) - EU Monitor **Policy shift** <https://www.eumonitor.eu/>
- Changes in regulation policy e.g. regarding labelling

Food information indicators

- Economist Intelligence unit's platform
- EUROSTAT : annual report of EU : <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-key-figures/w/ks-fk-23-001>
- Communication of food safety Emergence of new reliable communication tools for consumers <https://www.fda.gov/consumers/consumer-updates/food>
- **RASFF (public)**
- **EFSA**
- Social listening (e.g. food shortages for certain products)
- Rise in food disinformation on a specific topic (EU tools, fact-checkers)
- Increase in food borne illness from the implementation of miss or disinformation
- Changes in regulation & policy e.g. regarding GMO

(b) Geopolitical instability

Advancing economic globalization is currently hampered through newly established/changed borders, barriers, and limits.

- **War and conflict:** Disruptions of diplomatic relations and global markets; e.g., Russia-Ukraine raw materials
- **Fragmentation between nations:** Political stand-off/ trade embargos; e.g., BREXIT in EU, computer chips

Figure 3.12: Overview of indicators for geopolitical instability

War and conflict indicators

- **Related to Food trade / linking amount of import from conflict zones / Material flow**
- Number of countries in Europe import certain "products" from others -linked to the countries in conflict
- **Monitoring the shortage of ingredients**
- Materials for technology - size of production in comparison to rest of the world production
- Energy dependencies linked to food production
- Storage or preservation
- Food safety emergency response plan and crisis coordination
- **Monitoring of war & conflict zones**

Fragmentation between nations indicators

- **Number and type of trade embargos**
- **Fragmentation leads to higher prices... Food Access**
- Trade processes (time affecting shelf-life and waste)

3.2. Final list of indicators and corresponding data sources / databases

The key indicators and databases from the initial literature survey (sections 2 and 3) are first listed in Section 3.2.1, which is followed in Section 3.2.2 by the key indicators and databases identified from the LL3 workshop (Section 3.1).

As in Section 3.1 the indicators are grouped by driver/subdriver and ordered by STEEP classification.

3.2.1. Indicator list chosen by the FOODSAFER WP1 partners prior de workshop

SOCIAL DRIVERS

Consumer behaviour

Indicator	Data source
Dietary lifestyle food safety	Surveys conducted in 2021 and 2023 - https://smartproteinproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/Smart-Protein-European-Consumer-Survey_2023.pdf
Consumption various types food safety	FoodEx2 - https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/microstrategy/foodex2-level-1
Consumption novel foods food safety	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption-data
Amount food waste preservation safety	Eurostat - https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ENV_WASFW/bookmark/table?lang=en&bookmarkId=6231196e-cf3c-4e0b-88ce-a7eb958f6e3e&page=time:2021
Searches for information food safety	Google Trends e.g. https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?geo=GB&q=food%20safety&hl=en
new vegetarian/vegan restaurants safety	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/structural-business-statistics/database
Cleaning food preparation surfaces kitchenware	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0956713519306668

Demographic development

Indicator	Data source
Degree of urbanisation food safety	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.URB.TOTL.IN.ZS
Population size food safety	https://data.oecd.org/pop/population.htm

Immigration/Emigration food safety	https://www.migrationdataportal.org/international-data?i=stock_abs &t=2020
Education rate food safety habits	https://data.oecd.org/eduatt/population-with-tertiary-education.htm
Gap rich poor food safety	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living conditions in Europe - income distribution and income inequality
vulnerable groups food safety	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption-data

Health and wellbeing (of human beings)

Indicator	Data source
Colon cancer rates food safety	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/hlth_cd_aro/default/table?lang=en
Occurrence of NCDs food safety	https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/
Life expectancy food safety	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_r_mlifexp/default/table?lang=en
allergies or intolerances food safety	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/all.15560
antibiotic dispensing/use food safety	https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/Antimicrobial-consumption-in-the-EU-Annual-Epidemiological-Report-2019.pdf
agricultural management practices food safety	https://datam.irc.ec.europa.eu/datam/area/FS_MONITORING

TECHNOLOGICAL DRIVERS

Technologies in food processing

Indicator	Data source
RASFF alerts food packaging	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/search <i>Search Instructions: To find data for your specific indicator, go to the search page, find the "Product Category" filter, and select "food contact materials".</i>
Emergence new technologies food safety	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/emerging-risks

minimally processed foods food safety, amount of convenience food	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/prodcom/database
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Technologies in food production

Indicator	Data source
Share of GMO cultivation / genetic modified plants mycotoxins, traits	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/applications/gmo
cell-based food production food safety / cell-based food approved market entrance	<p>https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/novel-food/authorisations/union-list-novel-foods_en https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/applications/novel-food</p> <p><i>To track "market entrance" and "food safety" status for cell-based foods, you should apply specific filters within the Open EFSA portal: Food Sector Area: Select "Novel Foods." Keyword Search: Use terms like "cell culture," "cultivated," or "lab-grown." Status Tracking: The portal shows whether an application is "Under consideration," "Safety assessment ongoing," or "Finished" (which leads to the final Commission decision for market entrance).</i></p>
total crop production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EUROSTAT utilised agricultural area - EUROSTAT Harvested production
Dairy food production food safety	<p>https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/european-union-one-health-2024-zoonoses-report</p> <p><i>This data source is ideal for tracking emerging risks in dairy production because it allows you to filter for specific safety metrics: Pathogen Prevalence: Look for sections on Listeria monocytogenes, Campylobacter, and Salmonella specifically in "Milk and Dairy Products." Raw Milk Risks: The report provides specific data on outbreaks and contamination levels in raw (unpasteurized) milk, which is a key sub-indicator for dairy safety trends. Non-compliance Rates: It tracks the percentage of dairy samples that fail to meet EU microbiological criteria (Regulation EC No 2073/2005).</i></p>
Meat production food safety	

	<p>https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/european-union-one-health-2024-zoonoses-report</p> <p><i>This source is particularly effective because it allows for granular tracking of meat safety across different production stages:</i></p> <p><i>Slaughterhouse Data: You can track the proportion of samples positive for pathogens during the slaughtering process, which is a key indicator of hygiene technology effectiveness.</i></p> <p><i>Retail/Market Sampling: Data on meat products at the retail level indicates the safety of the final product entering the food chain.</i></p> <p><i>Antibiotic Resistance (AMR): A critical sub-indicator for meat production safety is the monitoring of AMR in food-producing animals and meat, which EFSA tracks in the same reporting framework.</i></p>
Fishing & aquaculture production	<p>—</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/fisheries/database</p> <p>https://eumofa.eu/</p>
indoor – outdoor production food safety rates	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/14415042</p> <p><i>The "CHEFS" database (or the raw EFSA data streams) provides the granular detail needed to establish "rates" of safety incidents:</i></p> <p><i>Pesticide Residues: You can compare residue levels for the same crop (e.g., tomatoes or strawberries) grown in greenhouses (indoor) vs. open fields (outdoor). Greenhouse production typically shows different pesticide profiles due to the controlled environment.</i></p> <p><i>Microbiological Pathogens: This data allows you to track if certain pathogens (like Salmonella or Listeria) are more prevalent in hydroponic/indoor systems (where water recirculation is a factor) compared to soil-based outdoor systems.</i></p> <p><i>Search Strategy: In the Zenodo files, look for metadata fields such as prodMethod or growingCondition which classify samples into "protected" (indoor) or "unprotected" (outdoor).</i></p>
Organic production food safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EUROSTAT organic production of animal products - EUROSTAT area under organic farming - EUROSTAT organic production by crops - FAOSTAT
dioxin and mycotoxins in feed	

	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/resources/data-collection-chemicals
Veterinary drug use food safety	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/news/veterinary-drug-residues-food-whats-latest-eu
Water use agriculture food safety	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/portals/water-information-system-for-europe-wise#:~:text=Description,projects%20and%20research%20activities..

ECONOMIC DRIVERS

Distribution

Indicator	Data source
International trade in good statistics	EUROSTAT
Economic globalisation indicators food safety	EUROSTAT
Outdoor temperature food safety	IBM/weather data base
Amount published about data sharing	PUBMED/Scopus

ENVIRONMENTAL DRIVERS

Environmental contamination

Indicator	Data source
Ammonia Emission by agriculture	https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-eusdi/regionaleusustainabledevelopmentindicatorsforireland2022/goal2zerohunger/#:~:text=SDG 02 60%20measures%20the%20amount%20of%20ammonia%20(NH,inline%20with%20the%20CAP%20indicator%20C46.
Pesticides fertilizers sold food safety	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Agri-environmental indicator - mineral fertiliser consumption#:~:text=Highlights,see%20link%20to%20dataset%20below.

Microplastic concentration soil water safety	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC139633/JRC139633_01.pdf
Air quality measurements food safety	https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/air-pollution/who-air-quality-database/2022
Land use coverage area frame	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/lucas
municipal wastewater irrigation food safety	https://www.fao.org/aquastat/en/overview/methodology/wastewater
Food loss waste index safety	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_wasfw/default/table?lang=en

Management of (natural) resources

Indicator	Data source
Waste collection facilities	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_wasfac/default/table?lang=en
Landfill tax levels	https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/overview-of-landfill-taxes-on
Waste recycling rates	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/page/cei_wm011
Material prices for recyclates	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Recycling_%E2%80%93_secondary_material_price_indicator

Bioprocesses indicators

Indicator	Data source
organic fertilizers manure agriculture safety	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/manure-and-soil-biodiversity#:~:text=This%20dataset%20includes%20the%20spatial%20distribution%20of,review%20interactions%20between%20Manure%20and%20Soil%20biodiversity
Heavy metals soil food safety	

	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/lucas-heavy-metals
Nutrient composition of soil (C, N, P)	BORIS - Bodeninformationssystem (umweltbundesamt.at)
Microbial quality of water and soil	https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/WISE_SoE/wise2
Pest monitoring food safety	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/pest-surveillance#:~:text=To%20help%20EU%20Member%20States,methods%20for%20detection%20and%20identification.
Spread of zoonotic diseases food	https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/european-union-one-health-2024-zoonoses-report

3.2.2 Indicator list selected from the LL3 workshop

SOCIAL DRIVERS

(a) Consumer behavior:

Dietary choice:

- Consumption per Capita food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption>

Dietary lifestyle:

- Omnivore food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption#:~:text=The%20EFSA%20Comprehensive%20European%20Food,How%20to%20use%20the%20database> The primary repository for EU dietary data. While it contains segments for "Vegetarians," the "**All Subjects**" or "**All Consumers**" filter represents the baseline omnivore population, providing specific intake data for meat, fish, eggs, and dairy.
- Vegetarian food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption>
- Flexitarian food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption> The official repository for dietary data. Under the "**EU Menu**" project (updated Dec 2024/2025), it now includes specific population subgroups that identify as "meat-reducers" or "flexitarians," providing granular intake data for both conventional and alternative foods.

- Novel protein sources food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/novel-food#:~:text=Yes%2C%20any%20novel%20food%20that,to%20inform%20those%20at%20risk>.
- new vegetarian food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25#:~:text=Published%2C%20March%20and%202022%20April%202025>.
- vegan restaurants food safety. <https://www.food.gov.uk/uk-food-hygiene-rating-data-api#:~:text=Examples%20of%20how%20to%20use,Opens%20in%20a%20new%20window>.
- emerging Novel food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/emerging-risks#:~:text=EFSA%20publishes%20reports%20on%20identifying,interactions%20of%20emerging%20biological%20risks>.
- people illnesses food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/plain-language-summary/european-union-one-health-2024-zoonoses-report#:~:text=Salmonella%20spp.%2C%20norovirus%20and%20Campylobacter,the%20highest%20number%20of%20cases>. Published in **December 2025**, this is the definitive record of foodborne illnesses for the current cycle. It provides confirmed case counts, hospitalization rates, and fatalities for the top pathogens (Campylobacter, Salmonella, STEC, Listeria).
- National Census data food safety. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/population-demography/demography-population-stock-balance/database> The central repository for EU-wide census and population data. It provides high-resolution data on **demographics (age/sex), urban/rural splits, and educational levels**, all of which are primary variables in food safety vulnerability models.

Consumer knowledge:

- Cleaning food preparation surfaces kitchenware. <https://www.food.gov.uk/research/food-and-you-2/food-and-you-2-wave-9>
- QRhow often people search. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25>
- Consumer trends linked knowledge. https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2025-09/2025%20EB%20103.3%20EFSA%20Report_vfinal.pdf
- Survey Health Benefits food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25> Published in **September 2025**, this survey specifically includes a section on "**Healthy diets vs. food safety.**" It tracks whether consumers prioritize nutritional benefits, safety risks, or balance both equally.
- Survey cooking hygienic practices. <https://www.food.gov.uk/research/food-and-you-2/food-and-you-2-wave-10>

Consumer awareness / attitude:

- food lost and food preservation. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25> Includes specific sections on consumer understanding of "use by" vs. "best before" dates, attitudes toward food waste, and food management behaviors (e.g., storage and preservation).
- people local farmer's shops safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25> Trust Levels: Specifically measures consumer trust in "Farmers and primary producers" (consistently ranked high at 82%) and "Supermarkets or local grocers" (60%). Perception of Responsibility: Identifies who consumers believe is responsible for safety in the food chain (from farm to shop).

Public awareness:

- sales labelled product food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25>
- Consumer selection/ranking of various dietary behaviours to improve health. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25>
This report includes a dedicated section on "Diet and health according to EU citizens" (Chapter II, Section 5). It provides a ranked list of behaviors consumers believe are important for a healthy diet.
<https://www.foodtimes.eu/consumers-and-health/eurobarometer-2025-on-food-safety/>
- Data - SafeConsume HE Project -- Survey and data collection <https://safeconsume.eu/>
Specific report: <https://bucketeer-1b3b1b88-cf85-4aa0-a741-bdde50da98c4.s3.amazonaws.com/public/downloads/Project-summary.pdf>
Eurobarometer on Food Safety in EU - data on consumer behavior/awareness <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/it/corporate/pub/eurobarometer22>
Interactive Data Dashboard Visualizations of survey datasets and models on consumer food risks across Europe: <https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/safeconsume.viz/vizzes>
Scientific Dataset (PMC) Raw data (\$N=1,973\$) regarding consumer beliefs, efficacy myths, and food safety behaviors: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9006754/>

(b) Demographic development

Population change:

- Demographics of population food safety.
The EU One Health Zoonoses Report (2024/2025 Edition). The most comprehensive data source is the **EU One Health Zoonoses Report**, jointly published by **EFSA** and the **ECDC**. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/infographics/foodborne-diseases-europe-whats-really-making-you-sick>
- Population size food safety. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/population-demography/>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption>
- Data - Immigration - European Commission, Eurostat,. <https://data.oecd.org/pop/population.htm> <https://population.un.org/wpp/>

Prevalence of vulnerable groups:

- metabolism coronary diseases food safety. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/the-state-of-cardiovascular-health-in-the-european-union_ea7a15f4-en.html
- cancer food safety. <https://ecis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/data-explorer#/>
<https://monographs.iarc.who.int/>

Urbanisation:

- Degree urbanization Eurostat food safety. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/degree-of-urbanisation/database>
- Education rate food consumption habits. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/health>
Daily consumption of fruit and vegetables by sex, age and educational attainment level:
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/hlth_ehis_fv3e/default/table?lang=en

Social welfare:

- Gap rich poor food safety.
The most robust data source is the Eurostat Database on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC). This source provides the specific metric "Inability to afford a meal with meat, chicken, fish (or vegetarian equivalent) every second day."
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/income-and-living-conditions/database>
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_mdcs03/default/table?lang=en
- Purchase behavior food safety.
The most comprehensive data source is the Special Eurobarometer: Food Safety in the EU (and its subsequent 2025 updates).
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25>

Migration:

- Legislation migration food safety. https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/official-controls-and-enforcement_en

(c) Health and wellbeing (of human beings)

Human health condition:

- Occurrence NCDs food safety. https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/health-promotion-knowledge-gateway/eu-burden-non-communicable-diseases-key-risk-factors_en
<https://gateway.euro.who.int/en/>
- Colon cancer rates food safety (FAO, EFFSA) . <https://ecis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/data-explorer#/estimates>
<https://apps.who.int/food-additives-contaminants-jecfa-database/>
Data - FAO, EFFSA, Dept of Health , National surveys linking disease to food intake: <https://www.sciensano.be/en/projects/national-food-consumption-survey#physical-activity-and-sedentary-behaviour>
<https://www.sciensano.be/en/health-information>

Perceived human health condition:

- allergies intolerances surveys food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25> The prevalence, cost and basis of food allergy across Europe: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/514000/reporting>

Resistant pests and diseases:

- antibiotic dispensing use food safety. <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/antimicrobial-consumption/surveillance-and-disease-data/database>
- agricultural management practices food safety. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Agri-environmental_indicator_-_consumption_of_pesticides
Crop statistics: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/org_cropar/default/table

TECHNOLOGICAL DRIVERS

(a) Technologies in food production

Primary production:

- fertilizer waste water food safety Purchase innovative machines food safety.
The most comprehensive and publicly accessible data source is the European Commission's DataM platform, specifically the "Technologies in Agriculture and Food Safety" dashboard: <https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/area/TECHNOLOGIES>
Also see:
<https://www.cema-agri.org/market-trends/market-data>
- Global fish production food safety. <https://www.fao.org/in-action/globefish/en/>
- high intensity farming food safety. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Agri-environmental_indicators
- high antibiotics use food safety. <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/news/new-data-antimicrobials-sales-use-animals->

Plant-derived food production:

- vegetarian/vegan population food safety.
https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/area/FS_MONITORING
<https://gfi.europa.org/industry/european-consumer-insights-on-the-alternative-protein-sector/>

Products for food production:

- Purchase innovative pesticides food safety.
Data: https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database_en

Bioengineering:

- Production GMO foods food safety. https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/genetically-modified-organisms/gmo-register_en

Novel food sources:

- consumption rates novel foods safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption>
https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/novel-food/authorisations/union-list-novel-foods_en
- Fermented foods industry safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/qps>
<https://zenodo.org/communities/efsa-kj/>
- Fermented foods home safety.
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25>

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/infographics/2025-eurobarometer-food-safety-eu-infographic>

- Novel food applications to EFSA.
<https://open.efsa.europa.eu/> Navigate to the questions page. In the "Food Domain" or "Topic" filter, select "Novel Food". This will generate a live list of every novel food application currently being processed by the European Union.
- Summary of applications and notifications https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/novel-food/authorisations/summary-applications-and-notifications_en
- Production rates food supplements safety. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Industrial_production_statistics
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/prodcom/database>

(b) Technologies in food processing

Processing techniques and scale:

- Data - Digital media monitoring EUM EMM Overview
<https://emm.newsbrief.eu/NewsBrief/alertedition/en/ECnews.html>
<https://medisys.newsbrief.eu/medisys/homeedition/en/home.html>
- TIM tool (TIM analytics | TIM analytics | Knowledge for policy (europa.eu))
- new foods market food safety.
https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/area/FS_MONITORING
- retail stores food safety.
https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/mashup/EU_FOOD_SYSTEM_MONITORING/
<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/search>
- cultured meat food safety. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/items/94b21367-e1ee-4448-a65e-f40595862253>
<https://open.efsa.europa.eu/questions?search=novel+food>

Food packaging:

- Plastics Europe food safety. <https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/>
<https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/plastics-the-fast-facts-2025/>
- Enabling a sustainable future, TIM tool (TIM analytics | TIM analytics | Knowledge for policy (europa.eu))
- RASFF: migration alerts Food contact materials, alerts packaging.
<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/search>. Go to the Search tab. Under Product Category, select "Food contact materials". In the Hazard or Subject field, type "Migration". This will return a list of every official notification where packaging chemicals exceeded legal safety limits. https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/eu-reference-laboratory-food-contact-materials_en

Upcycling for food:

- Data - annual reporting , Food waste at EU DG Sante: food waste platform Food waste reduction targets - European Commission (europa.eu)

New technologies:

- Precision Fermentation food safety. <https://www.fao.org/food-safety/scientific-advice/biotechnology--gmo-and-gm-foods/cell-based-food-and-precision-fermentation/en>
- Data - Novel food catalogue <https://ec.europa.eu/food/food-feed-portal/screen/novel-food-catalogue/search>

ECONOMIC DRIVERS

(a) Distribution

Global trade:

- Imports in euros food safety.
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/page/TEIET120>
[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Extra-EU trade in agricultural goods](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Extra-EU_trade_in_agricultural_goods)
- Exports in euros food safety.
[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EXT LT INTERTRD/default/table](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EXT_LT_INTERTRD/default/table)
[https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis en](https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis_en)
- Data - FAO, WTO, Sanitary & Phytosanitary measures, <https://databank.worldbank.org/>, ECDC EFSA outbreak reports, Economicst Intelligence unit platform for trade/commodity/economy data

Distribution channels:

- Sales data food safety.
- <https://www.nisra.gov.uk/statistics/business-statistics/broad-economy-sales-and-exports-statistics> , Consumer studies

New distribution channels:

- Online shops food safety.
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25>
[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/isoc r ec eseln2/default/table?lang=en](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/isoc_r_ec_eseln2/default/table?lang=en)
- Novel delivery food safety.
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/eurobarometer25>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/infographics/2025-eurobarometer-food-safety-eu-infographic>

Food fraud:

Data - JRC Tech report (EC) , RASFF alerts , <https://www.safefood.net/> safefood is an all-island body, set up under the British-Irish Agreement Act 1999 , Food Fraud Database <https://www.foodchainid.com/products/food-fraud-database/> , https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/eu-agri-food-fraud-network_en

Storage:

- Energy costs food safety.
https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/mashup/EU_FOOD_SYSTEM_MONITORING/
<https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/resource/data-trends-of-the-european-food-and-drink-industry-2026/> Electricity prices for non-household consumers - bi-annual data
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_pc_205/default/table?lang=en
- Storage space food safety.
https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/mashup/EU_FOOD_SYSTEM_MONITORING/
<https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/europe-food-cold-chain-logistics-market>

The TRACES platform maintains a database of Authorized Establishments, which includes a list of all cold stores and warehouses approved to handle animal-origin products. https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/traces_en

ENVIRONMENTAL DRIVERS

(a) Environmental contamination

Agricultural pollution:

- Chemical Fertilizer Usage food safety. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Agri-environmental_indicator_-_mineral_fertiliser_consumption
<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/european-zero-pollution-dashboards/indicators/health-impacts-of-contaminants-from-fertilisers-signal-1>
- Nitrate concentration water food safety.
<https://water.jrc.ec.europa.eu/portal/apps/dashboards/cb6034c2a75e4df282f8a62f90c16caa>
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/SDG_06_40/default/table?lang=en
- Pesticides sold food safety.
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/aei_fm_salpest09/default/table
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/AEI_HRI_custom_3027590/default/table?lang=en

- Fertilizers sold food safety.
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/AEI_FM_USEFERT/default/table
<https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DataPortal/fertiliser.html>
- Usage antibiotics sales food safety Data - reports, sales data, social media, newspaper articles, Reports Antibiotic sales and AMR doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7209 (AMR); + ESVAC report (sales data)

Pollution:

- Fossil fuel share food safety.
https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/mashup/EU_FOOD_SYSTEM_MONITORING/
[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Final energy consumption in industry - detailed statistics](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Final_energy_consumption_in_industry_-_detailed_statistics)
- Microbial contamination food safety.
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/microstrategy/FBO-dashboard>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/plain-language-summary/european-union-one-health-2024-zoonoses-report>

Sewage treatment:

- waste water treatment food safety.
<https://water.europa.eu/freshwater/freshwater/countries/uwwt>
<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/urban-waste-water-treatment-in-europe>
- sewage treatment plants food safety. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/urban-waste-water-directive-treatment-data-viewer-urban-wastewater-treatment-directive-1>
- Quality sewage plants food safety Production of struvite food safety. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02019R1009-20241120>
<https://www.phosphorusplatform.eu/activities/regulatory-activities>
Life Cycle Inventories of Struvite: <https://zenodo.org/records/14810939>
- Data - HydroWASTE <https://www.hydrosheds.org/products/hydrowaste>
- Home | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations <https://www.fao.org/aquastat/en/overview/methodology/wastewater>
- Global wastewater database <https://www.iwmi.cgiar.org/2014/06/global-wastewater-database/>

Waste management:

- Recycling rate food safety.
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00063/default/table>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/food-contact-materials>

- Data - FAO on global level , Your gateway to the EU, News, Highlights | European Union <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/waste/data/database>

(b) Management of (natural) resources

Recycling:

- National record industries food safety. https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/chemical-safety/food-contact-materials/plastic-recycling_en
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00063/default/table>
- Recycling rate food safety (eurostat). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/cei_wm020/default/table
- Rapid Alert recalls. <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/list>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/webinar-rapid-assessment-contaminant-exposure-race-tool>
- non-compliance food contact material legislation. https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/chemical-safety/food-contact-materials/plastic-recycling_en
<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/list>
- Use waste stream food safety. https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/chemical-safety/food-contact-materials/plastic-recycling_en
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/cei_wm011/default/table
- organic fertilizers food safety agriculture. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02019R1009-20241120>
<https://www.compostnetwork.info/policy/from-waste/fertilising-products-regulation/>
- Use manure agriculture food safety. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/nitrates_en
<https://water.jrc.ec.europa.eu/portal/apps/dashboards/cb6034c2a75e4df282f8a62f90c16caa>
<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/manure-and-soil-biodiversity>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/microstrategy/FBO-dashboard>

Waste and soil management:

- Plastics soils microplastics food safety. <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/euso/euso-dashboard>
- Proportion of land used for animal farming (FAO). <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data>
<https://www.fao.org/gleam/en/>
- Predictions pesticides sales food safety (OECD). <https://data-explorer.oecd.org/?tm=Pesticides%20use%2Fsales&pg=0&snb=10>
- Nutrient composition of soil (C, N, P) - BORIS - Bodeninformationssystem <https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/boris>
- Eutrophication of water bodies (European Marine Observation and Data Network - EMOD). <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/search/node?keys=eutrophication>

- Microbial quality water soil safety. <https://esdac.irc.ec.europa.eu/euso/euso-dashboard>
<https://esdac.irc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-biodiversity-dna-bacteria-and-fungi>
- Data - <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-023-00967-2> Analysis of microplastics (umweltbundesamt.at) , FAO, OECD, BORIS, EMOD.

(b) Bioprocesses

Transboundary pests and diseases:

- Bio-vectors Climate change food safety. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/climate-change-and-food-safety>
- Number of confiscated food (Databases of airports and marine ports). <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/search> In the "Notification basis" filter, select "Border control - consignment detained" or "Border control - consignment destroyed".
https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/plant-health-and-biosecurity/europhyt/interceptions_en
<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/tracesnt/directory/listing/establishment/publication/index#!/search> TRACES NT Public Directory Provides the list of all approved Border Control Posts (BCPs) at airports and marine ports where confiscations occur.
- Scale FOODI trade food safety. https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/traces_en
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/international-trade-in-goods/database>
- Data - Modelling using diff. Data, Pathogen monitoring reports (Animal and Plants) .
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/monitoring-foodborne-diseases>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/powerbi/plant-health-horizon-scanning-dashboard>

Bio-accumulation:

- Antimicrobial residues food safety. https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/chemical-safety/residues-veterinary-medicinal-products_en
- Presence Bacteria Water food safety. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub/datahubitem-view/fbf3717c-cd7b-4785-933a-d0cf510542e1> <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/foodborne-zoonotic-diseases>
- Accumulation contaminant bees food safety. <https://www.insignia-bee.eu/>
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/pesticides>

- Accumulation contaminant worms food safety.
<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/node/66354>
<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7226>

POLITICAL DRIVERS

(a) Legislation, policies and governance

Monitoring and communication of food safety:

- Data - Digital media monitoring EUM EMM Overview (newsbrief.eu) / TIM tool (TIM analytics | TIM analytics | Knowledge for policy (europa.eu)) - Social listening
- Belgian food safety authority barometer to communicate with stakeholders on food safety : <https://www.favv-afsca.be/scientificcommittee/barometer/>
- Annual national reports on food safety (e.g. in Austria).
<https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/lebensmittel/lebensmittelkontrolle.html>
[https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/dam/jcr:44ab2f8a-d303-4be3-add5-7f059ab192fc/Food Safety Report 2022.pdf](https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/dam/jcr:44ab2f8a-d303-4be3-add5-7f059ab192fc/Food_Safety_Report_2022.pdf)
- The European Union One Health 2022 Zoonoses Report;
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/8442>
- Monitoring of veterinary drugs EU https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/chemical-safety/residues-veterinary-medicinal-products_en
- Pesticides data programme annual report from EFSA:
<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/7939>
- food fraud monitoring in EU JRC reports :
https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/food-fraud-quality/monthly-food-fraud-summary-reports_en
- EFSA zoonoses report annual <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/8442>
- <https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/Lebensmittel/lebensmittelkontrolle/LMSi cherheit.html>
- Pesticide Data Program | Agricultural Marketing Service (usda.gov)
- RASFF (for authorities).
<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/search>
Filter by "Notification Basis" (e.g., official control on the market, company's own check) and "Risk Decision" (serious vs. non-serious) to monitor the governance performance of different Member States.
https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/eu-agri-food-fraud-network/reports-and-publications_en
- FDA Total Diet Study (TDS) <https://www.fda.gov/food/reference-databases-and-monitoring-programs-food/fda-total-diet-study-tds>

- Belgium FAVV - Productterugroepingen (favv-afsca.be)
- The European Union Summary Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in zoonotic and indicator bacteria from humans, animals and food in 2020/2021: <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7867>
- Zoonotic agents, German database: <https://zoonotify.bfr.berlin/>

Good practises and standards:

- Data - Alimentarius <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/codex-texts/list-standards/en/>
- EU platform on guidance platform : https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/biological-safety/food-hygiene/guidance-platform_en

Food legislation:

- Data - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/veterinary-regulatory-overview/research-and-development-veterinary-medicines/maximum-residue-limits-mrl#ema-inpage-item-10712>
- EU regulation <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/homepage.html>
- EU database pesticide https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database_en
- EU database additives regulation <https://ec.europa.eu/food/food-feed-portal/screen/food-additives/search>
- EU Monitor: Always up to date with the latest developments with the EU [Monitor/1/j9tvgajcovz8izf_j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vk0qgtdhw4yx](https://www.eumonitor.nl/9353000)
<https://www.eumonitor.nl/9353000>
- Policy shift <https://www.eumonitor.eu/>

Food information:

- Data - EUROSTAT : annual report of EU : <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-key-figures/w/ks-fk-23-001>
- Communication of food safety Emergence of new reliable communication tools for consumers <https://www.fda.gov/consumers/consumer-updates/food>
- RASFF (public), EFSA. <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/search>
<https://open.efsa.europa.eu/>

(b) geopolitical instability

War and conflict:

Food trade warfood safety.
<https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/Ukraine/Ukraine.html>

https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/eu-agri-food-fraud-network/reports-and-publications_en

- import conflict zones food safety. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2019/1793/oj/eng Primary Data Source: European Commission - Regulation (EU) 2019/1793 (Regularly Updated Annexes)
- Shortage ingredients war food safety. <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/dataportal/food-supply-security.html> Primary Data Source: European Food Security Crisis Preparedness and Response Mechanism (EFSCM) Dashboards.

Fragmentation between nations:

- Trade embargos food safety. <https://www.sanctionsmap.eu/>
https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/enforcement-and-protection/trade-defence/monitoring-trade-diversion_en
- Food Access fragmentation food safety. <https://www.fao.org/gIEWS/food-prices/home/en/>

Tracks "Price Anomalies" and food policy changes globally.

<https://data.irc.ec.europa.eu/collection/id-00434>

4. Discussion: Databases and their characteristics, accessibility and relevance to indicators.

Firstly, we make the observation that data is a valued and often monetized resource, especially for specialized sectors. With this in context, the available online databases for indicators that are directly or indirectly related with food safety emergence can be classified with respect to the limitations made by the database owners on how they can be accessed.

For the purposes of the current work, we can classify online databases as follows: (i) only query with predefined templates, keywords and pull-down list categories; (ii) allows free format queries directly to the data; (iii) plus download of results in a csv format or similar; (iv) plus download of results in a csv format or similar; (v) combinations of (i) to (iv) with API interface access.

From what we have analysed, the majority of the online databases do not provide API interfaces, the most habitual interface is type (i).

From this classification, next, we can consider how we can access the database from the IT Platform front end (developed in WP4): (a) just provide the link to the online database, the user clicks on the link and then follows the instructions and functionality of the database; (b) plus provide to the user with a set of predefined queries (which could be in the form of a help/readme file specific for each database and for the indicators chosen in this deliverable); (c) Some kind of API programming interface between the online database.

Given the mentioned restrictions, the options which seem most feasible within the scope of the current project are (a) and (b).

5. Interface requirements to integrate databases and indicator data with the Open Digital Hub and tasks developed in WP4.

In close collaboration with Task 1.2, an ‘alert system’ tool will be built in the open digital hub (WP4). This is a scalable tool that consists of an interactive dashboard that displays the real-time values of the indicators (based on the underlying data) so that they can follow the trends in the indicators via graphs. Users will also set up the alerts feature so that they are notified if indicators move out of the normal range of values. As stated in the Task 1.2 definition, there are specific matters to be tackled:

5.1. Linking of data to the open digital hub (WP4)

The data will be linked to the open digital hub (WP4), such that the platform dashboard displays the real-time values of the indicators, based on underlying data. For this to be possible, in T1.2 the existence of a data source and viability of access will be evaluated for each indicator. Also, data format will be evaluated (e.g. sufficient time series data from previous periods, monthly, yearly to make it possible to identify trends, etc.). Accessibility will be a key challenge: what type of interface is offered to the given data source/database by the data owners.

5.2. Database crawling and analysis.

In the context of the Foodsafer project, we interpret the database crawling in terms of the work done by the food safety experts in order to identify the key indicators and associated data sources, using a combination of manual search and automated techniques.

The crawling of database is a specific IT technique which is dependent on accessibility and data privacy issues, as well as data availability. A generic web crawling process is illustrated in Fig. 5.1

Fig. 5.1: Schematic of generic web crawler steps

Corresponding FoodSafer steps

1. Food safety experts identify key indicators and corresponding data source links/websites (WP1)

2. In platform, construct index of key indicators and corresponding data source links/websites (WP4)

3. In platform, define front end screens to access and query indicators and data source links (WP4)

FoodSafer knowledge repository and analytics

4. Query results and information can be selected and stored by user (WP4)

5. User can perform analytics using machine learning and statistical techniques (WP4)

Fig. 5.2: Specific Foodsafer web crawling steps.

Fig. 5.2 illustrates the steps applied in the foodsafer project. In a first step the food safety experts identify key indicators and associated databases, which comprises the result detailed in Section 3 of this document and forms part of the work done in WP1. Next, in steps 2 and 3, the IT platform incorporates the links (index) and front end user screens which allow access and querying. In steps 4 and 5, the results can be stored and accumulated progressively in an information repository, which can then be processed by different analytical techniques to provide insights, identify trends, make predictions, etc. The storage and analytics may also be provided by individual websites which are linked to the platform.

5.2.1 Database crawling – considerations.

Legal issues: while doing web crawling for one's purposes, then it is legal as it falls under the fair use doctrine such as market research and academic research. However, if you want to use scraped data for third parties, especially for commercial purposes, this can have legal complications. In the United States, for instance, web scraping can be considered legal as long as it does not infringe upon the Computer Fraud and Abuse Act (CFAA), the Digital Millennium Copyright Act (DMCA), or violate any terms of service agreements.

Different examples of database crawling applications were tested. For example, Google Trends, which was evaluated as a proof of concept (Fig. 5.2), and it was decided not to use it.

Fig. 5.3: Google Trends proof of concept embedded into the platform.

With the Google Trends approach embedded in the platform, the user could identify the most relevant food safety signal trends worldwide. Also, the Workspaces could be set up to engage and discuss the identified indicators chosen for this report, in order to start collaborative strategies on discussion boards. In next steps (WP4) and given the change in direction of not including those features (Fig. 5.3), further evaluation of approaches will be done, to incorporate in the IT platform developed).

6. Conclusions, summary, next steps

This deliverable document has provided a summary of the drivers, subdrivers and indicators selected from the work embodied in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2. From this, a study and selection of available databases have been made, which provide information relevant to the indicators identified. This provides a working document for the implementation of the open digital hub interface to the data repositories, which will be developed in WP4.

References

- [1] AGES. <https://www.ages.at/en/>
- [2] Risk Ranger (https://foodsafetyportal.eu/riskranger/rr_riskranger.html).
- [3] European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/data>
- [4] Surveillance Atlas of Infectious Diseases. <https://atlas.ecdc.europa.eu/public/index.aspx>
- [5] EFSA website. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en>
- [6]. International Journal of Food Microbiology, (Vol. 77, Issues 1-2, pp.39-53, 2002)
- [7]. FAO Fisheries Technical Paper (No. 442, 2004).

Appendices

In the following example screens are shown for search criteria in different databases.

A.1 FAOSTAT

The screenshot shows the FAOSTAT website interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the FAO logo and the text 'Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations'. A search bar is located in the top right corner. Below the header, there are navigation tabs: 'Data', 'Selected Indicators', 'Compare Data', 'Definitions and Standards', and 'FAQ'. The main content area is titled 'Search Data' and shows the search results for the query 'Consumer behaviour Dietary choice'. The results are listed as follows:

Search Result	Show Data	Download Data
Consumer Prices, General Indices (2015 = 100) (Item) ① Consumer Price Indices (Prices)	Yes	Yes
Consumer Prices, Food Indices (2015 = 100) (Item) ① Consumer Price Indices (Prices)	Yes	Yes
Recovered post-consumer wood (Item) ① Forestry Production and Trade (Forestry)	Yes	Yes

Fig. A.1.4 - FAOSTAT search, keywords “Consumer behaviour Dietary choice”

The screenshot shows the FAOSTAT website interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the FAO logo and the text 'Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations'. A search bar is located in the top right corner. Below the header, there are navigation tabs: 'Data', 'Selected Indicators', 'Compare Data', 'Definitions and Standards', and 'FAQ'. The main content area is titled 'Search Data' and shows the search results for the query 'Health and wellbeing Human health cor...'. The results are listed as follows:

Search Result	Show Data	Download Data
Cost of a healthy diet (PPP dollar per person per day) (Item) ① Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet (CoAHD) (Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet)	Yes	Yes
Percentage of the population unable to afford a healthy diet (percent) (Item) ① Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet (CoAHD) (Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet)	Yes	Yes
Number of people unable to afford a healthy diet (million) (Item) ① Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet (CoAHD) (Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet)	Yes	Yes
World Health Organization (WHO) (Donor) ① Development Flows to Agriculture (Investment)	Yes	Yes

Fig. A.1.2 - FAOSTAT search, keywords “health and wellbeing Human health cor...”

العربية 中文 English Français Русский Español

FAOSTAT

Home Data Selected Indicators Compare Data Definitions and Standards FAQ

Search Data

RESULTS

Demographic development Population

Temperature change (Element) Temperature change on land (Land, Inputs and Sustainability)	Show Data	Download Data
Land Use change + (Total) (Item) Emissions totals (Climate Change: Agrifood systems emissions)	Show Data	Download Data
Land Use change (Item) Emissions shares (Climate Change: Agrifood systems emissions)	Show Data	Download Data
Carbon stock change in forests + (Total) (Item) Emissions from Forests (Climate Change: Agrifood systems emissions)	Show Data	Download Data

Fig. A.1.3 - FAOSTAT search, keywords “Demographic development Population..”

العربية 中文 English Français Русский Español

FAOSTAT

Home Data Selected Indicators Compare Data Definitions and Standards FAQ

Search Data

RESULTS

Environmental contamination Pollution

Environmental protection (General Government) (Item) Government Expenditure (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data
Environmental protection (Central Government) (Item) Government Expenditure (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data
General Environmental Protection, unspecified (Purpose) Development Flows to Agriculture (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data
Environmental policy and administrative management (Purpose) Development Flows to Agriculture (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data

Fig. A.1.4 - FAOSTAT search, keywords “Environmental contamination Pollution”

FAOSTAT

Home Data Selected Indicators Compare Data Definitions and Standards FAQ

Search Data

RESULTS

Q food production technology products

Per capita food production variability (constant 2014-2016 thousand int\$ per capita) (Item) ① Suite of Food Security Indicators (Food Security and Nutrition)	Show Data	Download Data
Food crop production (Purpose) ① Development Flows to Agriculture (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data
Value Added (Manufacture of food, beverages and tobacco products) (Item) ① Macro Indicators (Macro-Economic Indicators)	Show Data	Download Data
Manufacture of food, beverages and tobacco products (Industry) ① Value shares by industry and primary factors (Food Value Chain)	Show Data	Download Data
Food security and food safety + (Total) (Purpose) ① Development Flows to Agriculture (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data

Fig. A.1.5 - FAOSTAT search, keywords “food production technology products”

FAOSTAT

Home Data Selected Indicators Compare Data Definitions and Standards FAQ

Search Data

RESULTS

Q distribution global trade

Coefficient of variation of habitual caloric consumption distribution (real number) (Item) ① Suite of Food Security Indicators (Food Security and Nutrition)	Show Data	Download Data
Incidence of caloric losses at retail distribution level (percent) (Item) ① Suite of Food Security Indicators (Food Security and Nutrition)	Show Data	Download Data
Global Alliance for Vaccines and Immunization (GAVI) (Donor) ① Development Flows to Agriculture (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data
Global Environment Facility (GEF) (Donor) ① Development Flows to Agriculture (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data
Global Fund (Donor) ① Development Flows to Agriculture (Investment)	Show Data	Download Data

Fig. A.1.6 - FAOSTAT search, keywords “distribution global trade”

A.2 RASFF

The screenshot shows the TIM interface with the following details:

- Navigation:** Organisation, Location, Topic, News, Quantitative Analysis, Miscellaneous.
- Dataset Info:** Documents, Organisations, edit.
- User:** David Nettleton (Logout).
- Search:** Article (selected), EU Project. Filters: Date, Type, 1993-2020, highlight text.
- Results (12 documents):**
 - Determinants of consumers' choice behaviour for fresh fish types** (Year: 2020)
 - Integrating nutrition science and consumer behaviour into future food policy** (Year: 2019)
 - Smoothies: Exploring the Attitudes, Beliefs and Behaviours of Consumers and Non-Consumers** (Year: 2018)
 - Muslim Consumers' Halal Product Choice Behaviour: An Eye-Tracking Investigation on Visual Choice Process** (Year: 2017)
 - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF BEHAVIOURS RELATED TO FUNCTIONAL FOODS AMONG SELECTED YOUNG CONSUMERS IN POLAND AND GERMANY** (Year: 2016)
 - Towards an Integrated Approach to Food Behaviour: Meat Consumption and Substitution, From Context to Consumers** (Year: 2016)
 - Shaping smarter consumer behaviour and food choice** (Year: 2016)

Fig. A.2.1 - RASFF query, “Determinants of consumers’ choice behaviour for fresh fish types”

The screenshot shows the TIM interface with the following details:

- Navigation:** Organisation, Location, Topic, News, Quantitative Analysis, Miscellaneous.
- Dataset Info:** Documents, Organisations, edit.
- User:** David Nettleton (Logout).
- Search:** Article (selected), EU Project. Filters: Date, Type, 2007-2022, highlight text.
- Results (12 documents):**
 - Trade and the equitability of global food nutrient distribution** (Year: 2018)
 - Economic and physical determinants of the global distributions of crop pests and pathogens** (Year: 2014)
 - Does Income and Income Distribution Determine Global Food and Beverage Products Trade** (Year: 2013)
 - History, Global Distribution, and Nutritional Importance of Citrus Fruits** (Year: 2012)
 - The Impact of domestic remittances on Households' Income Distribution in a context of Global Food Crisis** (Year: 2011)
 - Global Income Distribution and Poverty in the Absence of Agricultural Distortions** (Year: 2009)
 - Global productivity distribution and trade liberalisation: evidence from processed food industries** (Year: 2008)

Fig. A.2.2 - RASFF query, “Trade and the equitability of global food nutrient distribution”

TIM Tools for Innovation Monitoring
 Open Access

Organisation • Location • Topic • News • Quantitative Analysis • Miscellaneous

Rebuild Edit Export Page Info Class Filter Go to More

Dataset Info Documents Organisations edit

David Nettleton (Logout)
 David Nettleton's space
 CREATE Dataset

Dietary_choice
 distribution_global_trade
food_production_technology_products
 Human_health_condition
 manage_nat_resources_raw_material_cons
 Pollution
 Population_change
 war_conflict

Documents: 952

Article EU Project Patent

Date, Type 1951 2022 highlight text

Entry type	ID	Year
Article	e7c727295ee35a213f9341c392722a6b5b25a08	2022
Article	dcdfcd8dd8a346c2f30dc0237946186dd2dab3b	2022
Article	ca1245cbe45935ac60ad1bd240396e2507399827	2022
Article	b7604cdf32391581e49c7ecc48db70047fabe06	2022
Article	bd8d5f4a5ae55f8f3ddb3eb1a23422a353536b6	2022
Article	ab4b894eca5b853c4f1a74eb1af372069823ca9f	2022

Full screen

Fig. A.2.3 - RASFF query, “Development of waste-free production technologies for the food industry”

TIM Tools for Innovation Monitoring
 Open Access

Organisation • Location • Topic • News • Quantitative Analysis • Miscellaneous

Rebuild Edit Export Page Info Class Filter Go to More

Dataset Info Documents Organisations edit

David Nettleton (Logout)
 David Nettleton's space
 CREATE Dataset

Dietary_choice
Human_health_condition
 Pollution
 Population_change

Documents: 344

Article EU Project Patent

Date, Type 1962 2022 highlight text

Entry type	ID	Year
Article	eff6d3cb29c014d78e18711336cfe394d0132ac	2022
Article	cc5bbc73d10a6ec6ca62f87fa8c53edbeede1cdf	2022
Article	b1ee22011fe10569e00bed87343e5e0f63f256de	2022
Article	7e0e1ddb5971fdb5e0de25f63655ab41e7b1a9d	2022
Article	6d058999de85cfc8dd2ec0c8154a37abed3bb790	2022

Fig. A.2.4 - RASFF query, “Human health condition”

Tools for Innovation Monitoring
Open Access

David Nettleton (Logout)
David Nettleton's space

CREATE Dataset

- Dietary_choice
- distribution_global_trade
- Human_health_condition
- manage_nat_resources_raw_material_cons
- Pollution
- Population_change
- war_conflict

Organisation • Location • Topic • News • Quantitative Analysis • Miscellaneous

Rebuild Edit Export Page Info Class Filter Go to More

Dataset Info Documents Organisations edit

Documents: 70

Date, Type 1970 2022 highlight text

- Natural Resource Management and Nutrition Outcomes: A Quasi-experimental Evaluation of Fisheries Decentralisation in Laos
Entry type: Article ID: 8e18340f5bbd56961a7adbd07ea9af5b1670cd Year: 2022
- Environmental impacts of land management on the sustainability of natural resources in Oriental Erg Tunisia, North Africa
Entry type: Article ID: e47774356e47100913c77875ea833cb031c1142 Year: 2021
- Management of Regional Natural Resources based on the Variability of Environmental and Economic Indicators
Entry type: Article ID: c57f2531a3861a37b4fc98ac6d482020c8966eb5 Year: 2021
- How microalgal biotechnology can assist with the UN Sustainable Development Goals for natural resource management
Entry type: Article ID: bdd5edd44fb3c1e1cc29a07b80b62b1010e79f4 Year: 2021
- Natural Capital Accounting Informing Water Management Policies in Europe
Entry type: Article ID: b10953b192bb7d51fe9a8bea0a65842f378bc82c Year: 2021
- Accounting and Management of Natural Resource Consumption Based on Input-Output Method: A Global Bibliometric Analysis
Entry type: Article ID: 0f46c29f14b0ddf80223467bd337b47940803411 Year: 2021
- Investigation and Assessment of the Management of Natural Resources in the State of California Using the Conceptual Framework of Water–Energy–Food Nexus
Entry type: Article ID: deb0612302483f108f0216987041b76877452e3 Year: 2020

Full screen

Fig. A.2.4 - RASFF query, “management of natural resources raw materials..”

Tools for Innovation Monitoring
Open Access

David Nettleton (Logout)
David Nettleton's space

CREATE Dataset

- Dietary_choice
- Pollution
- Population_change

Organisation • Location • Topic • News • Quantitative Analysis • Miscellaneous

Rebuild Edit Export Page Info Class Filter Go to More

Dataset Info Documents Organisations edit

Documents: 449

Article EU Project Patent

Date, Type 1967 2022 highlight text

- Is public service transportation increase environmental contamination in China? The role of nuclear energy consumption and technological change
Entry type: Article ID: cd1ac23e106365d963a46fe2c4ea19021daab0f4 Year: 2022
- Natural and organic fertilizers as a source of environmental contamination with antimicrobial substances
Entry type: Article ID: a14587145a5a9e1915d602e685c8b8eedd5514d Year: 2022
- Distributive justice in environmental health hazards from industrial contamination: A systematic review of national and near-national assessments of social inequalities.
Entry type: Article ID: 93acdcd85cfd25ca28108e101f648b96a2953af Year: 2022
- Vertical distribution of heavy metals in Karewa deposits of South Kashmir: environmental contamination and health risk assessment
Entry type: Article ID: 45498f91eb553d5fca96b29b1048d9cdfa6262c7 Year: 2022
- Heavy Metal Contamination of Urban Mangrove Sediments and Their Environmental Significance in the Zhanjiang Bay
Entry type: Article ID: fbfe4970f6409f3365a6490c1e7fc1536cd6267c Year: 2021
- An Integrative Approach to Assess the Environmental Impacts of Gold Mining Contamination in the Amazon
Entry type: Article ID: efe42fe9750854543b92658d11d1cd035e694ffc Year: 2021
- Environmental Heavy Metal Contamination in Some Selected Cocoa Plantations in Oyo State, Nigeria
Entry type: Article ID: [Not fully visible] Year: [Not fully visible]

Full screen

Fig. A.2.5 - RASFF query, “Pollution”

David Nettleton (Logout)
David Nettleton's space

CREATE Dataset

- Dietary_choice
- Pollution
- Population_change

Full screen

Organisation • Location • Topic • News • Quantitative Analysis • Miscellaneous

Dataset Info Documents Organisations edit

Rebuild Edit Export Page Info Class Filter Go to More

Documents: 410

Date, Type 1959 2022 highlight text

Title	Entry type	ID	Year
Estimating the Demographic Parameters of Tuta absoluta (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) Using Temperature-Dependent Development Models and Their Validation under Flu...	RASFF	d4ccac9b98d1c9bee2867b96f4bda2ebdacdd0a	2022
Migration in the Context of the Demographic Development of the Russian Far East	RASFF	c4bb4b351d544efc6f5ddb1b1e82e09fd19ca537	2022
GIS-Based Spatial Correlation Analysis: Sustainable Development and Two Generations of Demographic Changes	RASFF	7844a995abdbef1780238397580bffc5c6340c4b	2022
The Effects of Demographic Trends on the High-Quality Development of the Chinese Sports Industry	RASFF	146349e9f761d4c76ea36c42284861645ae692cc	2022
Challenges and contradictions in the development of the North and the Arctic: demographic dimension	RASFF	0f11821f8183125e137f9c5447aebbbb82a4cfa	2022
Socio-Demographic Factors influencing the Sustainable Development of Carpathian Euroregion: Case of Tourism Development	RASFF	fd65bdf4fcd4cae78c6b62fd59be52983e577cfb	2021
Home-Based Learning (HBL) Teacher Readiness Scale: Instrument Development and Demographic Analysis	RASFF	f172ea59247296c1130292ef63b2580ebee3264a	2021

Fig. A.2.6 - RASFF query, "Population change"